

THE BASICS OF BALL VALVES DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This article is looking for the questions of the design different types of the ball valves and their constructive differences. The application of the ball valves differs and the basics of the design constructions is looking through the prism of the industrial needs. Ball valves may not bounce very well but they work great at regulating flow. The popular valve is named for its round ball that sits in the interior of the valve body and pushes into a seat to control or provide on/off functions in fluid pipelines.

The robustness and dependable performance of industrial ball valves make them useful in a wide range of industries, including water management and chemical processing. Processing engineers may find that replacing these valves after they malfunction as a result of misuse or general wear and tear is expensive and time-consuming. In order to maintain system functionality and optimal efficiency, we will address common reasons for industrial ball valve failure in this article along with industrial valve repair procedures. To avoid such failures in the future, it is essential to comprehend their underlying causes. Transportation and lubrication processes are just two of the many uses for industrial ball valves. High efficiency and resistance to extreme pressures and temperatures are features built into these valves. The spherical disc with a bore hole through it is used by the industrial valve to operate. Moving the lever handle causes the ball to rotate into either an open or closed position. This makes precise regulation of the flow of liquids or gases possible. Industrial ball valve wear and tear must be routinely checked for in order to preserve efficiency, and any required industrial valve repair work should be done right away when required.

Keywords: ball valves, design of ball valves, reliability of the ball valves, failure of ball valves, construction of ball valves, wear, tear, friction resistance.

API 6D trunnion ball valves.

The heritage of ball valves is much shorter compared to gate, globe and check valve designs. Although the first ball valve patent was issued in 1871, it would take another 85 years for ball valves to become a commercial success. The discovery of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, or “Teflon”) during the process design for manufacturing the atomic bomb in World War II, would be the catalyst that started the ball valve industry

rolling. Ball valves come in all materials from brass to carbon steel and stainless steel to zirconium.

There are two basic types: floating ball and trunnion ball. These two designs allow for the construction of effective ball valves from ¼” through 60” and larger. Generally, the floating design is used for smaller and lower-pressure valves, while the trunnion type is used for larger and higher-pressure valve applications.

Floating ball valve.

The reason for the two types of ball valves has to do with the way they seal and how the fluid force is distributed from the line flow to the ball and then to the seat. In the floating ball design, the ball is riding snugly between two seats, one upstream and one downstream. The force of the fluid acts on the ball to push it into the seat located in the downstream valve body. Since the ball covers the entire flow bore, all the force in the stream is pushing against the ball to force it into the seat. If the ball gets to be too large and the pressure too high, the force will be so great on the seat that the valve cannot be operated because the operating torque would be too high.

Floating ball valves come in a variety of body styles, although the two-piece, end entry type is the most popular. Other body styles include three-piece and top entry. Floating ball valves are manufactured in sizes up to 24" and class 300, but the practical realm of the floating ball valve is generally much lower—up to about 12".

Although ball valves are designed primarily to be on/off or "block" valves, the addition of partial ball and V-port ball designs can make them good choices for control-type applications.

RESILIENT SEATS

The smaller floating ball valves are found in many different applications from household plumbing to those containing the harshest chemicals. The most popular seating material in these valves is some form of thermoplastic, such as PTFE. PTFE seats work very well because they are soft enough to seal well on to the polished metallic ball, yet firm enough not to blow out of the valve. The two primary concerns with these soft-seated valves are that they are susceptible to scratching (and potential leakage) and are limited to temperatures below the melting point of the thermoplastic seats—somewhere around 450°F (232°C) depending on the exact seat material.

A ball valve "ball."

A feature of many resilient-seated floating ball valves is the ability to moderately seal in the event of a fire that causes the primary seats to melt. This is called a fire-safe design; it features a seat pocket that not only holds the resilient seat in place, but also provides a metallic seating surface that can provide a partial seal as it contacts the ball. The fire-safe design is confirmed by testing the valve in accordance with the American Petroleum Institute (API) 607 or 6FA fire-testing standards.

TRUNNION DESIGN

When larger sizes and higher-pressure ball valves are needed, the design shifts to the trunnion style. The trunnion differs from the floating style in that the trunnion ball is held in the body via a trunnion (short, attached stem) in the bottom and by the stem at the top. Since the ball cannot "float" into the seat to attain positive closure, the seat must float to the ball instead. The

trunnion seat is designed so that the seat is energized by the upstream pressure and is forced into the ball to seal. Because the ball is held securely in place, except for its 90° rotation, the extraordinary fluid force and pressure does not jam the ball into the seat. Instead, the force acts only on a small area on the periphery of the floating seat.

The trunnion ball valve is the brawny big brother to the floating ball valve and as such it gets to handle the big jobs—high pressures and large pipe diameters. By far the most popular use of trunnion ball valves is for pipeline service. These valves are especially popular in natural gas pipelines in diameters up to 60" and pressures up to class 600. Trunnion ball valves can also be used in higher pressures if required. By using trunnion designs the torque required to open and close the valve is lower, so smaller actuators can be used.

End-entry design.

The trunnion design also lends itself well to double block and bleed service since both the upstream and downstream seats float independently and most designs also feature a body or drain connection. Trunnion designs often employ seat lubrication ports where a lubricant can be injected around the seat to assist in closure efficacy.

METAL-SEATED DESIGNS

The biggest advancement in ball valve technology over the past 30 years or so is the metal-seated ball valve. While the idea of metal seats and a metal ball are not new—in fact, the first ball patent in 1871 featured a brass ball and brass seats—the design needed advancements in coating technology to really be perfected.

The metal-seated ball valve design has enabled ball valves to take a big chunk out of the market share

dominated for decades by the venerable gate valve. The metal-seated, specialty-coated ball closes tightly against a set of precision coated and lapped seats, providing zero-leakage, if the hardened seating surfaces are not scratched by debris in the line.

BALL VALVE STANDARDS

There are several standards that apply to ball valves. The following table lists the most common ball valve design documents:

Ball valves have made huge inroads in replacing other valve types over the past 40 years. The cost to manufacture the smaller sizes has dropped greatly as well, making them even more competitive. The advances in coatings and metal-seated ball valve technology have created very robust designs that have resulted in an attractive total cost of ownership.

Table 1.

Common ball valve standards

Standard #	Title	Organization	Type or service
API 608	Metal ball valves-flanged, threaded and welding ends	API	Refinery
API 6D	Pipeline valves	API	Pipeline
SP72	Ball valves with flanged or butt-welding ends for general service	MSS	General applications
SP110	Ball valves threaded, socket-welding, solder joint, grooved and flared ends	MSS	General applications
SP122	Plastic industrial ball valves	MSS	Plumbing and general applications
507-18	Ball valves, 6 in. through 60 in. (150 mm through 1,500 mm)	AWWA	Waterworks
521-18	Plastic ball valves	AWWA	Waterworks

Floating Ball Valve Design

With this design the ball is held between two ball seats by the compression of the seats against it. To turn the ball 90° or quarter turn the ball is driven by a shaft which connects to a slot in the top of the ball. The slot allows a little lateral movement of the ball due to the influence of upstream line pressure. The design principle around floating ball valves is that they are loaded

by line pressure against the downstream seat which is why this seat is always regarded as the primary seat. In some cases the upstream seat can also give a secondary seal if the design has a pre-loading or a spring in the the upstream seat design.

Trunnion Mounted Ball Valve Design

On this design the ball is supported by a trunnion and not the valve seats which allows much higher pressure and temperature ratings. The concept behind this is that the shaft and trunnion are intended as being a one piece construction. The shaft and trunnion are held in bearings to prevent the ball from moving against the downstream seat. To facilitate loading the upstream seat is designed to move forward against the ball and thus in a trunnion mounted ball valve the primary seat is formed at the upstream side. A spring mechanism is also incorporated behind both seats to ensure even seat loading even at low pressures and to provide a secondary seat on the downstream side. As with floating ball valve designs, trunnion mounted ball valves are capable of bi-directional shut off. One of the main benefits of trunnion mounted ball valves over floating ball valves is a lower operating torque and consequentially this means that actuation costs can be lower.

Different Ball Valve Body Designs

One Piece Ball Valve Design – The ball is placed into the body through an entry in one of the pipe flanges and secured with a gasket forming part of the raised face. This has inherent strength and minimises leak paths.

Split Body Ball Valve Design – This is also known as a 2 piece or 3 piece ball valve and the body is split in one or two places in the same plane as the valve flanges. The body is then bolted around the ball. 3 Piece ball valves are common among smaller sizes due to lower manufacturing costs and trunnion mounted ball valves due to component weight. The big advantage of split body ball valves is the ease of maintenance.

Top Entry Ball Valve Design – This is a rarer design of valve where the ball is inserted through a bonnet in the top of the valve. The main advantage of this is that the critical parts of the valve can be maintained while the valve remains in the pipeline. It's often used in welded pipe systems.

Fully Welded Ball Valve Design – This is where the body of the valve is an all welded construction and completely non-maintainable. These are often found used in gas pipelines.

The difference between Reduced or Full Port Ball Valves (also known as Full or Reduced Bore)

One of the most important considerations with a ball valve is port size. Full port generally means the ball port is the same as the inside diameter of the pipe. One of the advantages of Reduced Bore Ball Valves is that they are lighter in weight and cost less but the disadvantage is a reduced flow and in some cases a 1 piece construction rendering them non-maintainable.

Anti-Static Ball Valves

If the ball is held between seats without any metallic contact between it and other components the flow of fluid can lead to a build up of static electrical charge on the surface of the ball. To prevent this static forming a spark, igniting fluid or causing an explosion valve design standards require a mechanism to ensure electrical continuity between ball, body and downstream pipe-work.

Anti-Blowout Design

In the floating ball valve design the shaft is not attached to the ball. It is essential to make sure that the shaft cannot be blown out past the packing if the gland bolting is removed or slackened.

Fire Testing of Ball Valves

As the majority of ball valves rely on soft seats in order to seal properly, engineers are often concerned about whether a ball valve will still operate in the event of a fire which has partially damaged or destroyed the ball seats. For certain industries like oil, chemical and petrochemical industries it's a requirement that valve can still operate. Ball valve fire safe standards stipulate the details of fire to which a ball valve must be subjected to before it can be certified as 'fire tested'.

Ball Valve Cavity Relief

When a ball valve is closed the body cavity of a ball valve is full of line fluid which can always escape if the pressure is not sufficient to load the ball onto the downstream seat. In this case an increase in temperature may render the valve inoperable due to the increase in temperature, and as a solution to over pressure relief, a hole can be drilled in the upstream side which renders the valve uni-directional. Cavity relief is part of the design in a trunnion type ball valve but not inherent in a floating ball valve so required adding.

Lined Ball Valves

These are a type of ball valve which is manufactured for corrosion resistance on services like acid. The wetted internal contact parts of the valve usually have a PFA or PTFE lining inside a metal body with the ball being fully lined to or made from ceramics. If the lining is damaged in any way the less corrosion resistant body will end up being exposed to the line fluid.

Low Temperature Ball Valves

Specific low temperature ball valves are used for low temperature and cryogenic applications like LPG, and LNG. These are usually low temperature carbon steel but more frequently stainless steel has been standardised by manufacturers for this service, going as low as -196°C . Cryogenic valves often suffer from higher operating torques due to the PTFE ball seats contracting at this temperature and another standard feature is an extended bonnet. This isolates the gland seals from the low temperature to avoid ice formation and maintain the integrity of the seal.

The most common materials for ball valve manufacture are carbon steel grades WCB and LCB for the body and stainless steel grade 316 or CF8M for the ball and shaft. In special applications the body can be made from stainless alloys in corrosive or low/high temperature applications.

The standard seat material for ball valves is PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene) because it is chemically inert to a wide range of fluids and has a coefficient of friction at less than 0.1.

PTFE loses rigidity at high temperatures which is why Ball valves have a pressure/temperature curve supplied by the manufacture showing what temperature is achievable at what pressure.

To overcome the limitations of standard PTFE, special Nylons, Polyether-etherketone (PEEK) and powder filled PTFE's are used to gain a higher rigidity

over the seating face and an increase in maximum service temperature. When temperatures are over 280°C metal seated ball valves are required.

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